

Review of Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories

Dattatraya

February 10, 2025

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How can economics be related to the Earth?

This was the question in my mind when I read the title of the book Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories by Quan-Hoang Vuong and Minh-Hoang Nguyen. I got the answer by reading the initial chapters of the book. This book contains invaluable information on measures that need to be created and implemented to minimize the continuous climate change, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation of our planet Earth. The book can be treated as a research project and discusses the changes required to be made in our economics and its thinking to heal the Earth. Being scientists, the authors have studied and analyzed 348 references to present the crucial subject in the form of this book, which is a conclusive report of the present condition of the Earth and the neglect of the same by economists, corporate businesses, government agencies, and also the people.

The book poses a crucial question: "Why are governments, business owners, and entrepreneurs still reluctant to change economic and business models that are driving the Earth towards the edge of climate tipping points and planetary boundaries?" And to answer this the authors have discussed the need to reexamine how the current global economic system is operated. The authors have shed light on the ineffectiveness of the traditional conservation approach in preventing the environmental disruption caused by the ever-rising desire for economic development and growth.

The initial three chapters of the book provide a thorough discussion of the assumptions of the economists and established economic principles, while further chapters contain the discussion about learning from the quantum and information theories and considering a new definition of value, which can help economists change their principles and methods. The book elaborates on the factors behind the unprecedented heat experienced by the world and the average CO2 concentration in the atmosphere reaching a new high in 2024. Additionally, the concept of innovation claimed to have the potential to improve quality of life while using fewer and fewer of our natural resources and emitting less and less carbon dioxide by discovering new and cleaner sources of energy, the carbon credit market implemented worldwide to reduce CHG emissions, and the rising conversion of land use, mainly through deforestation, driven by the desire for economic growth, are discussed in depth. The chapter "Shifting value paradigm for healing the Earth" presents the establishment of an Eco-Surplus Culture, which, when ingrained in humanity's mindset, will serve as a benchmark for the information processing system, including sociocultural and economic systems, to accept a new conception of growth.

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Review of Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories

by **Dattatraya** » 10 Feb 2025, 10:22

[Following is a volunteer review of "Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories" by Quan-Hoang Vuong, Minh-Hoang Nguyen.]

How can economics be related to the Earth?
This was the question in my mind when I read the title of the book *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories* by Quan-Hoang Vuong and Minh-Hoang Nguyen. I got the answer by reading the initial chapters of the book. This book contains invaluable information on measures that need to be created and implemented to minimize the continuous climate change, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation of our planet Earth. The book can be treated as a research project and discusses the changes required to be made in our economics and its thinking to heal the Earth. Being scientists, the authors have studied and analyzed 348 references to present the crucial subject in the form of this book, which is a conclusive report of the present condition of the Earth and the neglect of the same by economists,

5 out of 5 stars

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Screenshot. A volunteer review of “*Better Economics for the Earth*” by Dattatraya on February 10, 2025 [1].

The scientific discussion of all the factors related to climate change and biodiversity loss on our planet Earth is the main positive aspect of the book. The authors have explained how the economists from all schools have generally disregarded the relevance of environmental problems to their work. They say, "Clearly, the rapid economic development in the past few centuries has made economists confident to the point of arrogance." The authors have explained how this arrogance lets them ignore a fact: from its inception to the present, humanity has survived and thrived based on natural sources and ecological values provided by the Earth. The example of penguin price given to show how the economists' limited understanding of nature and measurement tools neglect climate change and biodiversity loss, is well suited.

I appreciate the authors for their brave reference to the political stand of frequently prioritizing economic growth and undermining the climate and biodiversity loss crises by giving an example of a typical political figure namely former President Donald Trump of the United States (U.S.). It will be better to read the same in the book.

I also appreciate the point of eating habits of people, like the consumption of luxurious beef and rare wildlife, for the sake of social prestige, social identity, and business advantages that add to environmental degradation through the release of methane gas, which has 28 times greater global warming potential than carbon dioxide.

The inclusion of various figures in the book significantly aids in understanding key points and ideas. In particular, Figure 3 is highly effective in illustrating the principles suggested by the authors, which can help leverage the power of the humanities and social sciences in addressing environmental problems and building an Eco-Surplus Culture.

I didn't find any negative aspects in the book. The editing of the book is professional with excellent work.

I appreciate the authors' hard work, the accuracy of their references, and their strong desire to make readers aware of the movement of the Earth towards the edge of climate tipping points and planetary boundaries. I am happy to rate this book 5 out of 5 stars.

I recommend this book to all readers. I believe that everybody who reads this book will get full knowledge of the present condition of climate change and the biodiversity loss on our planet Earth and understand its seriousness.

(*) Note: This paper reprints Dattatraya's volunteer review [1] appearing on Online Book Club of the title [2].

References

[1] Dattatraya. (2025, Feb. 10). Review of Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories.

<https://forums.onlinebookclub.org/viewtopic.php?f=24&t=616076>

[2] Vuong, Q. H. & Nguyen, M. H. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>